

ISic1353

I.Sicily inscription 1353

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8746

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140855

1. [ένθ]άδε κίτε
2. [Εύσ]έβλιος πρεσ-
3. [βύτ] ερος, πατήρ
4. [— — — — —]
- 5.

Edition: PHI140856

1. ...πρεσ-
2. [βύτ] ερος, πατήρ
3. [συναγωγής(?)]
- 4.

Edition: PHI337192

1. [ένθ]άδε κίτε
2. [Εύσ]έβλιος πρεσ-
3. [βύτ]ερος, πατήρ
4. [τῆς συναγωγής(?)].
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492966

EDCS 39101731

PHI 140855

PHI 140856

PHI 337192

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0534 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 52.0883

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.

Vatican. At no.440

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